

Order of elemental analysis

*You can bring your samples (min 5 mg) to Sylvie (lab 07) on Mondays and Thursdays **between 9:30am and 11:00am***

Customer

Name: Giacomo Manfroni	Date: 15.02.2022
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Sample

Sample name: MAG188(2)	
Aspect / texture: yellow crystalline solid	
Molecular formula: C ₂₆ H ₂₆ O ₄	Molar mass: 402.49
Used solvent: CHCl ₃ , DMF, Et ₂ O	
Structure:	

Sample details

Is the sample harmful? (skin, lungs, toxic)	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Is the sample light sensitive?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Is the sample electrostatic?	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
Is the sample hygroscopic?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Do you want your sample back?	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
Additional informations:		

Elemental analysis

Sample name: MAG188(2)

Single determination

Double determination

C <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	H <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	N <input type="checkbox"/>
Other elements:		

Results

Analysis number: 2022-08			
Sample name: MAG188(2)			
Expected values:	C 77.59 %	H 6.51 %	N 0 %
Results:	C 77.34 % 77.41 %	H 6.48 % 6.55 %	N 0 % 0 %
	Other elements:		
Remarks: Because I had a problem with the EA device, I measure your sample twice!			

Date/Visa operator
 01.03.2022, Sylvie Mittelheisser